

A Show of Force: The Ritualization of Russian Strategic Posturing in the Baltic Sea

MARIIA VLADYMYROVA*

University of Copenhagen, Denmark

This article studies military exercises as tools of strategic posturing, understood here as physically embodied, spatially configured, and visually defined coercive signaling action which commonly entails symbolic attributes. By identifying the modalities of ritualization involved in the conduct of military exercises, the article unfolds how these modalities render military activity a politically meaningful action and contribute to the construction of the displayed capabilities as credible deterrent. I argue that the spatial emplacement of strategic posturing is a key element for credibility in general deterrence. This proposition is empirically grounded in the examination of Russian naval exercises in the Baltic Sea in the years 2022–2025. The analysis accentuates how Russian strategic posturing engaged spatiality to project and sustain credibility vis-à-vis NATO as the security tensions between two actors increasingly manifest in the maritime domain.

Este artículo estudia los ejercicios militares como herramientas de posturas estratégicas, entendidas como acciones de señalización coercitiva físicamente incorporadas, configuradas espacialmente y definidas visualmente, que, con frecuencia, implican atributos simbólicos. El artículo identifica las modalidades de ritualización involucradas en la realización de ejercicios militares, lo que nos permite desentrañar cómo estas modalidades hacen que la actividad militar sea una acción políticamente significativa y contribuyen a la construcción de las capacidades mostradas como un elemento disuasivo creíble. Argumentamos que la ubicación espacial de la postura estratégica es un elemento clave para la credibilidad en la disuasión general. Esta propuesta está fundamentada empíricamente en el análisis de los ejercicios navales rusos en el Mar Báltico entre los años 2022 y 2025. El análisis destaca cómo la postura estratégica rusa utilizó la espacialidad con el fin de proyectar y mantener la credibilidad frente a la OTAN, mientras las tensiones de seguridad entre ambos actores se manifiestan cada vez más en el ámbito marítimo.

Cet article étudie les exercices militaires en tant qu'outils de positionnement stratégique, entendu ici comme une action de signalement coercitif incarné physiquement, configuré spatialement et défini visuellement qui implique couramment des attributs symboliques. En identifiant les modalités de la ritualisation impliquées dans la conduite des exercices militaires, l'article décortique comment ces modalités transforment les agissements militaires en actions significatives sur le plan politique et contribuent à la construction de capacités affichées comme moyens de dissuasion crédibles. J'affirme que l'emplacement spatial du positionnement stratégique constitue un élément clé de la crédibilité en dissuasion générale. Cette proposition s'ancre empiriquement dans l'examen des exercices navals russes dans la mer Baltique entre 2022 et 2025. L'analyse souligne le fait que le positionnement russe fait appel à la spatialité pour projeter et entretenir une certaine crédibilité vis-à-vis de l'OTAN, alors que les tensions de sécurité entre les deux acteurs se manifestent de plus en plus dans le domaine maritime.

Keywords: deterrence; coercive signaling; military exercises; Baltic Sea; Russia.

Introduction

Military exercises serve purposes beyond preparing troops for combat. In various strategic contexts, they can build trust, foster alliances or send coercive signals to adversaries (Heuser and Simpson 2017). In post-Cold War Europe, Russia was the first to revive large-scale military exercises in 1999 (Heuser et al. 2018, 5–6). Since 2008, the Russian Armed Forces have conducted annual theater-level exercises. In 2013, the so-called snap exercises were introduced, which come with no prior notification and often involve large numbers of personnel (Norberg 2018). In both cases, Moscow has routinely evaded the Vienna Document's observation requirements by under-reporting troop numbers and exploiting other loopholes, thereby undermining the transparency regime the agreement was meant to ensure (cf. Schmitt 2018; Hughes 2021). The increase in Russian military training activities and the lack of transparency, along with aggressive interventions in Georgia and Ukraine, have raised concerns

about the state's assertive posture in Europe (cf. Clem 2018; Norberg 2018).¹

The signaling purpose of Russian military exercises is particularly notable: deterrent messages are deliberately embedded in both conventional and nuclear forces' training scenarios. The Baltic region and High North are especially common venues for such exercises (Clem 2018; Ratsiborynska et al. 2020; Åtland et al. 2022; 2024; Heier 2025; Friis 2025). Since 2019, the Baltic Sea has become a recurring venue for Russian strategic naval exercises, culminating in "Ocean-2024," reportedly the largest since 1991 (Bott 2024). The spatial patterns evident in Russian military activity point to an overlooked dimension in deterrence theory. Scholars have de-

¹For Russia, exercises have also served to obscure outright military aggression. In 2008, what Moscow claimed to be routine training maneuvers "Kavkaz-2008" ultimately served as staging for the intervention in Georgia (Allison 2009); in 2014, Russia launched a major military exercise in its Western and Southern Military Districts to dissuade any other actor from intervening in Ukraine as their "little green men" intervened in Crimea (Norberg 2014). In 2022, the Russo-Belarusian joint exercise "Union Resolve" prepared the north-western axis of Russian advance to Kyiv two weeks prior to the full-scale invasion of Ukraine (Woodward 2024, 35, 73–76).

*Corresponding author: University of Copenhagen, Denmark. Email: vla@ifs.ku.dk

voted extensive attention to mechanisms of coercive signaling and their influence on audiences' perception of an actor's deterrence (e.g., Jervis 1970; Fearon 1997; Slantchev 2011; Gartzke et al. 2017; Schelling [1966] 2020; Mälksoo 2021). Yet the question of how spatiality shapes deterrence practice has remained largely implicit.

This article studies Russian naval exercises in the Baltic Sea during 2022–2025 as ritualized and spatially configured coercive signaling practices. My argument builds on “thick geopolitics” (Toal 2017, 243) which rejects the view of space as a fixed backdrop where physical geography determines politics. Instead, this perspective highlights how actors intersubjectively produce geopolitical space through their interactions across both material and imagined geographies. To develop my argument, I argue coercive signaling follows a distinct, ritualized logic of action (cf. Mälksoo 2021).

Actors' military activity functions as a form of coercive signaling—what I term a posturing action—through the ritualized modalities of enactment: the embodied, visually defined, and spatially configured presence; the patterned execution of actions; and the occasional use of symbolic attributes. Actors embed deterrent commitments and threats into specific localities, while these localities, in turn, shape the meaning of the message conveyed through posturing, as their strategic positioning, historical associations, and symbolic resonance become integral to credibility projection. Geography functions not as a passive backdrop but as a co-constitutive element in deterrent interactions, as actors' dispositions toward and perceptions of space actively shape strategic contestation and intersubjectively enact these spaces as geostrategic.

The Baltic Sea provides an empirical context to illustrate this argument, as it is characterized by the high political salience of both symbolic performances and material force displays shaping the deterrent interactions between Russia and NATO. After 2014, NATO has been gradually scaling up its force deployments in the Baltic region in response to Russia's increasingly assertive posture (cf. Clem 2018; Veebel and Ploom 2019; Banka and Busmann 2023). The Baltic region emerges both as the center of gravity for the allied forward presence, and has acquired symbolic value for NATO's “reinvention” of extended deterrence (Mälksoo 2024). In 2023, tensions escalated around Moscow's so-called “shadow fleet” of aged vessels sailing under dubious flag registries to bypass international sanctions. The alleged involvement of these vessels in damaging critical subsea infrastructure in the Baltic Sea prompted NATO to launch the “Baltic Sentry” maritime patrol mission in 2025, signaling a sharper deterrence posture against Russian illicit activity (Ringbom and Lott 2024; NATO SHAPE 2025a). These intensifying dynamics of mutual strategic posturing heighten the risk of military-to-military or military-to-civilian incidents.²

The spatial dimension is consequential in rendering these mutual posturing meaningful as coercive signaling: by situating its shows of force in the Baltic Sea close to NATO coastal states territorial waters or infrastructural sites, Russia amplifies the visibility and immediacy of its discontent with NATO's presence at its doorstep. Russian Deputy Foreign Minister Alexander Grushko stated in January 2025: “[. . .] NATO's desire to turn the Baltic Sea into a NATO lake, a metaphor they like to use in public statements. However, this

will not happen for many reasons, with the main one being because Russia will not allow it to happen” (TASS 2025a).

Two significant limitations to my argument should be noted. First, I treat military exercises as the most expressive form of strategic posturing, while recognizing that other military activities, such as troop deployments, surveillance overflights, and maritime patrols, also contribute to posture-building, albeit in more routinized and less spectacular ways (cf. Mälksoo 2024; Vanderborcht 2024; Friis 2025). Second, I recognize that what threats actor perceive as credible, and the actors' ability to enact a credible threat emerge from the intersubjective understandings established in the course of deterrent interactions over time and geopolitical context (Lupovici 2010, 716). This study emphasizes credibility as *projected*. The focus is on outlining the performative, outward-facing staging efforts whereby an actor seeks to construct deterrent credibility through spatially embedded and ritualized signaling practices such as exercises, rather than on how signals are perceived or interpreted by their intended audiences, domestic or external.

The article is structured in four sections. First, I review three major scholarly approaches to the study of military exercises. Second, I discuss how to distinguish strategic posturing from coercive signaling as a broader category, highlighting the analytical implications of this distinction. Third, I outline the modalities of ritualization through which actors construct the projected credibility. Fourth, I present the empirical implications of the conceptual argument by analyzing Russian naval exercises conducted in the Baltic Sea between 2022 and 2025. I emphasize how the ritualized modalities of embodiment, regularity and spatial configuration, patterned ways of acting and symbolic attributes translate a military exercise to a politically salient posturing action, which contributes to Russian credibility projection efforts. The article concludes by summarizing the argument and outlining its implications for the study of NATO-Russia deterrence dynamics at sea in Europe. Ultimately, this article makes an empirical contribution by defining key patterns and spatial configurations of Russian naval exercises in the Baltic Sea. These observations further contextualize our understanding of the current deterrent interactions between NATO and Russia as strategic contestation increasingly pivots to the maritime domain.

Military Exercises: from a Training Routine to a Show of Force

Among various kinds of peacetime military activities, military exercises stand out as salient routines binding military organizations worldwide (cf. Barkawi 2011; Heuser and Simpson 2017). They range from the training of tactical units to large-scale, combined-arms events conducted at the state or even alliance level, typically following a regular cycle, often annual or biannual (cf. Heuser et al. 2018, 1–27; Norberg, 2024). But what exactly do we talk about when we talk about military exercises?

To a layperson, the notion of exercise might suggest an image of a routine rollcall, or some scenes of a military bootcamp workout. For a career servicemember, it might boil down to trivia like a meal shared in a foreign field during a drill. A politician may associate exercises with hours-intense tabletop simulation games and correspondent briefs and debriefs, or even with boredom while waiting for maneuvers to conclude at some remote site before they can address troops and honored guests with an official speech. For scholars, however, military exercises encompass all these aspects

²In May 2025, a Russian Su-35 fighter jet disrupted an Estonian Navy inspection of the sanctioned vessel *Jaguar*, which Estonia claimed to be on flagless navigation close to its territorial waters in the Baltic Sea (Reuters 2025). This brief standoff demonstrated Moscow's resolve to back the illicit maritime operations with naval force.

and more. As a social practice, military exercises provide a wealth of empirical data, informing various scholarly concerns in the study of strategy, military affairs and politics writ large (cf. Heuser et al. 2018, 24–25).

Military exercises can be generally defined as preparations for wars (Heuser et al. 2018, 11). In this sense, military exercises are planned, scenario-driven events that bring together personnel and assets in specific geographies designed to simulate operational conditions and anticipated threat environments. Military exercises aim to establish, enhance and display armed forces' readiness and capacity of their command-and-control structure to meet the challenges of real combat. Alongside their evident military utility, military exercises are rarely devoid of political intent (Heuser and Simpson 2017, 20–21).

In military exercises, actors present the “overt face” of their military organization which mostly remains “inert” during the peacetime (Heuser et al. 2018, 11). Whether involving different branches of a single military organization or multiple state actors, military exercises put actors' capabilities, doctrines and strategic narratives at public display. Therefore, the political ramifications of military exercises can extend far beyond their immediate training objectives. Thus, military exercises are equally performative actions—*shows of force*—that actively shape and reinforce perceptions and diagnoses of geopolitical circumstances among both participants and their audiences (cf. Mälksoo 2021; Norberg 2023; Friis 2025).

Military exercises enact battlespace; respectively, the emphasis is put on realistic enactment of conditions resembling those of an anticipated armed conflict, and less on capturing the political complexities of war (Irwin, 2005). Exercises often involve the physical assembly and maneuvering of troops under conditions designed to resemble a potential battlefield, incorporating factors such as terrain, weather, infrastructure, live fire, and electromagnetic environments. In military parlance, field exercises are considered the core of training practice, aimed at confronting the friction inherent in combat. Their purpose is stress test how troops conduct operations within the constraints of real environment, in line with “train where you fight” principle (cf. Depledge 2020). A prominent illustration is the recurrent maneuvers by Polish and Lithuanian forces, together with their NATO allies, along the Suwałki Gap, a forested land stretched along the Polish-Lithuanian border between Belarus and the Russian exclave of Kaliningrad. This corridor is widely regarded as a choke-point constraining operations and critical for military logistics going both ways in the event of a NATO–Russia armed conflict (cf. Reuters 2022; Lithuanian Armed Forces 2025).

Three Approaches to the Study of Military Exercises

Despite their significance in global politics, military exercises have attracted rather modest attention in international relations and strategic studies. Since the 2010s, a trend toward more systematic scholarly engagement with military exercises can be observed (cf. Heuser et al. 2018, 1–12). A notable surge in research interest over the past five years likely reflects the increasingly assertive global competition.³ For Europe, the focus is shaped by Russia's 2022 full-scale invasion of Ukraine and the intensification of below-threshold hostile activities in Europe often associated with Russia.

Within the body of research on military exercises three primary approaches can be identified. The first approach is represented by various disciplines of the “classic” curricu-

lum addressing operational art. The task is to discern the practical knowledge for warfighting which implies empirical granularity of these studies. Contributions cover a wide range of issues and are interdisciplinary, introducing insights from military history to formal modeling and operations research. Scholars ask what military exercises reveal about doctrine, operational concepts, and a state's force posture (Caravelli, 1983; Heuser, 1993, 2023; Wintermans and Cox 2022); how such exercises influence learning and group socialization within military institutions (Hedlund et al., 2015; Frazier and Hutto, 2017), and the role of military exercises in defense planning and force posture design (Washburn 1994).

Military exercises draw on the anticipated conflict scenarios and thus provide more than just an insight into operational planning and force posture. The tactics employed, capabilities demonstrated, scenarios rehearsed, locations designated, and the participants and observers involved give a sense of actors' threat perceptions, alliance dynamics, and the strategic environments they aim to shape (cf. Clem 2018; Ratsiborynska et al. 2020; Blackwell 2021; Åtland 2022, 2024; Norberg 2023). The second approach studies how military exercises matter politically for defense diplomacy, deterrence, assurance and confidence-building (Heuser et al. 2018). As such, military exercises are exemplary “costly” signals that are rendered credible by the virtue of cost and risk attached (cf. Schelling [1966] 2020, 108–125; Fearon 1997). As tools of diplomacy, joint military exercises in a non-allied setting can serve to recruit partners to join multinational war-fighting coalitions and facilitate confidence-building (cf. Blackwill and Legro 1989; Wolfley 2021; Kuo and Blankenship 2022; Galambos 2023; Dombrowski and Reich 2024). For the settings of extended deterrence, such endeavors are crucial to sustain commitments' and alliances' credibility (Depledge 2020; Banka and Bussmann 2023). In a tense security environment, military exercises might bear a potential for inadvertent escalation. A historical case in point is NATO's Able Archer exercise of 1983, which was nearly misinterpreted as the actual preparation for an all-out attack on the Soviet Union (Adamsky 2013; Heuser 2016; Fraise and Egeland 2023).

The third approach speaks to a broader constructivist call for a theorization of war as a socially generative force (Barkawi and Brighton 2011). From this standpoint, military exercises are seen as co-constitutive of actors' identities, beliefs and perceptions of “self” and “other,” as well as the political environments they interact within (Bousquet, Grove, and Shah 2020; Ventsel et al. 2021; Jude 2023; Vanderborcht 2024). Approached as a social practice, military exercises reveal ritual-like features that structure action and invest it with performative potency. Ritualization is evident in simulative, repetitive and formalized enactments of military exercises, makes their practice constitutive to routinizing warfare and rendering it an anticipatable event (Öberg 2020). Maria Mälksoo (2021) discusses how ritualization of military exercises render the otherwise abstracted performance of deterrence empirically observable, affectively relatable, and socially “real” for the deterring community as “a symbolic encounter with the Other.”

Building on this third approach, I now turn to the conceptual frame of analysis. First, I address the problem of credibility in general deterrence. Second, I identify the modalities of ritualization evident in strategic posturing as embodied and spatially configured signaling action. Third, I demonstrate how strategic posturing engages spatiality in projection of credibility through expressive ritualized performances.

³Semantic Scholar database search under the keyword “military exercises,” 24 November 2024.

General Deterrence, Credibility Projection and Strategic Posturing

Today, NATO–Russia relationship in the Baltic region remains best characterized as one of general deterrence. Patrick Morgan describes general deterrence as a condition of a latent conflict, where the primary goal is not to avert an imminent attack but to curb the potential for hostile actions altogether by shaping the adversary's strategic calculus in the long term (Morgan 2003, 80–87). In this way, general deterrence structures adversarial relationships over time. Thus, credibility relies less on momentous displays of force and resolve in a crisis, and more on sustained projections of threat and commitment structured through patterned and routinized military activity, declaratory policies actors enact and how they narrate the past crisis events. Such deliberate moves intended to construct and project the credibility of threats or commitments, thereby sustaining deterrence, are described as signals in deterrence theory (Schelling, 1960; [1966] 2020 146, 216; Jervis 1970; Morgan 2003, 101–105; 160–171; Mälksoo 2021). Not all military and diplomatic activity, explicitly verbalized or tacitly enacted, constitutes a signal, however. Signals are distinct in intentional and performative ways of acting (cf. Cohen, 1987; Vuori 2016; Mälksoo 2021). What transforms an action or statement into a deterrent signal is the convergence of actors' intent, modalities of action, audience reception, and situational context (cf. Jervis, 2017). Their respective intersubjective understandings established throughout deterrent interaction facilitate these interpretative processes (Lupovici 2010, 716).

Signaling appears to be empirically elusive in general deterrence. The baseline of “normal” military activity is relative to actors' assessment of their security environment. Morgan describes general deterrence as “an outgrowth of an overall military posture and the broad image it conveys” (Morgan 2003, 80–81). Thomas Schelling describes how credibility in general deterrence depends on continuity rather than urgency or specificity of deterrent threats and commitments:

“Particularly in the relations between major adversaries—between East and West—issues are decided not by who can bring the most force to bear in a locality, or on a particular issue, but by who is eventually willing to bring more force to bear or able to make it appear that more is forthcoming” (Schelling [1966] 2020, 94).

As a consequence, the credibility of a signaling action is more difficult to establish as well as to unambiguously assess: “Quite how general deterrence works we are not very sure, “it is a mystery” (Gray 2000, 23; cf. Morgan 2003, 81–83). In the absence of a crisis event, credibility is sustained by routine military activity and presence, such as surveillance and air policing missions, maritime patrols, military exercises, rotational and permanent force deployments (Morgan 2003, 87; Clem 2018, 132; Friis 2025). In this regard, I argue that credibility in general deterrence gravitates towards strategic posturing as an embodied, visually defined and spatially configured signaling action.⁴ Posturing means that:

“[...]one communicates by deed rather than words, or by deed in addition to words, and makes the actions form a pattern of communication in spite of the fact that each side is literate enough to understand what the other is saying” (Schelling [1966] 2020, 146).

Conversely, deviations from the established patterns may signal a shift in the deterrer's perceptions of security environment, prompting a recalibration of the adversary's own

⁴In some contexts, strategic posturing refers to the totality of a state's military assets—personnel, equipment, bases, and other infrastructure—also known under the label of force posture. More narrowly defined, strategic posture has been associated specifically with nuclear capabilities (Heuser 2023, 88).

stance. For strategic posturing, military exercises are exemplary practice. While orthodox deterrence scholarship agrees on the signaling function of military exercises, it rarely interrogates the underlying social logics at play. This is where a ritual lens on deterrence offers respite. I argue that strategic posturing relies on ritualized modalities, wherein its spatial configuration facilitates how credibility is projected to intended audiences.

The Ritual Logics and Spatial Grammar of Strategic Posturing

Robert Jervis suggested two categories, indices and signals, to differentiate between types of information that state actors rely on to interpret the actions and intentions of others (Jervis 1970, 21, 26). Signals are statements or actions whose meanings are established through tacit or explicit shared understanding between actors. While in this sense category of signals overlaps with indices, indices provide the evidence supporting the authenticity of the image being projected. Though the evidence might be false or incomplete, audiences grant it a degree of inherent credibility. These perceptions of authenticity are reinforced by the political cost of executing signals, which make manipulations appear impossible to the audiences, and a degree of unpredictability, since outcomes being not entirely under the actor's control (cf. Schelling [1966] 2020, 99–102).

Although military exercises are widely understood as signaling actions, focusing on their modalities of enactment—embodiment, spatial configuration, and claims to realism—reveals them more related to indices. Strategic posturing relies not solely on actors' interpretative conventions. A posturing action introduces material and tangible evidence of readiness and resolve, for example, troops deployment to establish a “trip-wire” (Schelling [1966] 2020, 47). Posturing performs an abstract political stance or a threat to reality, if only as simulated and temporary condition as in the case of military exercises. By enacting realistic simulations of warfare with armed forces assembled in conspicuous localities which are often associated with political sensitivities, actors amplify the adversaries' strategic concerns by introducing real-world risks, from potential casualties to major collisions and incidents (Clem 2018; Friis 2025; Heier 2025). Such activities may even trigger inadvertent escalation (cf. Posen 1982). As Raymond Cohen (1981, 84) points: “[Not only] warships, but also troops, missiles and aircraft are felt to possess communicatory credibility because their *emplacement* entails a relinquishment on the part of the initiator of future freedom of action: he has given hostages to fortune.”⁵

Military exercises can be understood as expressive performances in which the actions themselves embody and convey a tacit message (Cohen 1981, 82). Its political meaning as an act of strategic posturing is thus constructed as much through explicit verbalized declarations as through the modalities of its enactment: the embodied, visually defined, and spatially configured assembly of forces; the patterned execution of actions; and the introduction of symbolic attributes. Taken together, these elements demonstrate that strategic posturing follows a distinct logic of action—one that is ritual-like in nature. In this regard, consider how Roy Rappaport defines ritual: “[. . .] the performance of more or less invariant sequences of formal acts and utterances not entirely encoded by the performers” (Rappaport 1999, 24).

Ritual logic of action rests in the deliberate and strategic elevation of specific practices, setting them apart from ordi-

⁵Emphasis mine.

nary activity (Bell 1990, 302; 1992, 74, 89–90; cf. [1997] 2009, 81–83). This is achieved by means of ritualization which Bell (1992, 140) describes as a “way of acting that sets itself off from other ways of acting by virtue of the way in which it does what it does.” Ritualization is evident in formalism, traditionalism, invariance, rule-governance, symbolism, and performative modes of acting (Bell [1997] 2009, 81). While not exhaustive, these features help to recognize ritualized action across both religious and secular settings. Accordingly, strategic posturing in general and military exercises in particular fall within the category of ritualized action: it is a way of acting which is made *strategically* distinguishable from regular military activity by the context and modalities of its performance such as embodiment, regularity, patterned action performatively evoking anticipated combat scenarios, and symbolism.

Ritual, as Jonathan Z. Smith describes, performs the way things ought to be, maintaining a conscious tension with how things are: “what ought to happen has not, and this gap is both acknowledged and rationalized through ritual action” (Smith [1987] 1992, 109). Military exercises build on this ritual-like logic by simulating an anticipated conflict. By means of ritualized signaling, an actor enacts an idealized deterrent posture to compensate for the credibility gap which is inherent to general deterrence where no immediate crisis substantiates a threat or commitment as real. Smith further defines ritual as a mode of attention and as a category of emplacement (Smith [1987] 1992, 103–112). This twofold conceptualization emphasizes how spatial grammar configures ritual logic of strategic posturing. The structured ritual environment “directs attention” and facilitates how an action, ordinary and devoid of symbolic meaning otherwise, acquires its performative salience as a ritual action (cf. Tuan 1975).⁶

The significance of spatiality for the practice of deterrence remains largely implicit in deterrence theory. In discussion of bargaining, Schelling emphasizes that signals are often conveyed not through explicit statements, but in a tacit way through the pattern of action itself. For such signals to be effective, he argues, they must be simple, form a recognizable pattern, rely on conspicuous landmarks, and exploit distinctions that both parties understand. Features of geographic space, both natural and imagined, offer precisely such distinctions:

“[...]national boundaries and rivers, shorelines, the battle line itself, even parallels of latitude, the distinction between air and ground” can serve as obvious, if arbitrary, points of reference that make signals more discernable and credible (Schelling [1966] 2020, 136–138).

For Schelling, it is an *idiom* of military action:

“[...]the actions form a pattern of communication in spite of the fact that each side is literate enough to understand what the other is saying. There is something here in the psychology of communication—in people’s sense of proportion, of justice, of appropriateness, in the symbolic relation of a response to a provocation, in the pattern that is formed by a coherent set of actions—that goes beyond the abstract military relation between enemies, beyond the economics of cost and damage, beyond the words that are used to rationalize a set of actions” (Schelling [1966] 2020, 146–147).

In large-scale field exercises, an anticipated battlefield is enacted and structured geographically—“train where you fight” (cf. Depledge 2020); where such exercises take place is significant not only in replication of the topographic qualities of the terrain, or testing if logistic chains are combat-proof. Location holds equal importance for posturing credibility: when operational planning involves the deployment

of forces along geographical fault lines between adversaries, the planning process itself may generate escalatory risks before any active operations begin (Posen 1982). Another case in point are deliberate incursions in sovereign airspace or air-defense identification zones and risky interceptions; aggressive naval maneuvers in foreign states’ maritime economic exclusive zones close to their territorial waters, incursions in safety and protection zones for offshore infrastructure, as well as vessels’ shadowing maneuvers.⁷ All these actions demonstrate how spatial organization interacts with the deliberate manipulation of risk and ambiguity in deterrence.

A message conveyed by a posturing action becomes thus tied to its spatial context; its meaning is shaped profoundly by the politically relevant perceived implications of geography. Colin S. Gray pointed this out in his study of the relationship between deterrence and geopolitics: “[. . .]the notional geography of mental maps as imagined geography, can be even more important for political and strategic decision making than is physical geography itself” (Gray 2012). Crucially, credibility derives not merely from visible displays of capability, but from the symbolic, historical, and affective associations embedded in spatial settings—the idiom of “sacred soil.” This insight resonates with the central proposition of critical geopolitics that political actors understand geographic space beyond its physical features and jurisdictional boundaries. Instead, the geopolitical condition of international relations is continuously shaped through social practices and ideational representations of space as a locus of power (Agnew 1994; Tuathail 1999; Rech et al. 2015).

Troops carrying out maneuvers may not be consciously “bringing force to bear in a locality” to draw on the geopolitical significance of the place where they train (Schelling [1966] 2020, 94). But through the ritual-like logic and spatial grammar, the posturing action introduces material force and performatively embeds threats and commitments into the conspicuous localities. This makes strategic posturing meaningful as means of credibility projection in a co-constitutive relation to the geographic space. So constructed as a *place* of geostrategic significance, spatialized postures become affectively resonant for actors in a general deterrence relationship (cf. Mälksoo 2021, 2024; cf. Norberg 2023, 61–62).

For example, a series of NATO military exercises in 2025 “Griffin Lightning 25” focused on enhancing readiness and interoperability on the Alliance’s eastern flank. These involved specific drills like “Brave Boar” in Poland directly testing responses to threats in the vulnerable Suwałki Gap region, as well as “Hedgehog” in Võro county in the south-east of Estonia where forested terrain, lakes and marshlands create specific tactical challenges and replicate the anticipated environment where Russian aggression would need to be repelled. (NATO MNC NE 2025). Another example of the spatialized dynamic in credibility projection is NATO Secretary General Mark Rutte’s statement, which reads the uptick in Russian naval activity in the Baltic as evidence of NATO’s own enhanced resolve: “[. . .]the fact that the Russians are now really getting more and more active in the East Sea/Baltic Sea, is testimony to the fact that NATO is really getting its act together with our Allies” (Rutte 2025).

⁷Vessels and aircraft, including of military kind, operating seaward of a state’s territorial sea enjoy the freedoms of navigation and overflight and other internationally lawful uses of the sea related to those freedoms. For instance, military activities in foreign states’ exclusive economic zones (EEZs) are legally permissible, as sovereign rights there are limited to economic and conservation activities (Van Dyke 2004; Von Heinegg 2014; Beaucillon 2019). Nevertheless, states remain highly sensitive to such actions, not least due to their growing reliance on offshore critical infrastructure.

⁶While this approach to the definition of ritual might be reductionist, the interpretation of ritual action remains necessarily context dependent (Grimes 2006, 109–13).

Studying Strategic Posturing

Methodologically, military exercises can be tricky to study for they are not public events. Exercises are usually conducted far from civilian infrastructure and densely populated areas to minimize risks, thereby restricting opportunities for casual observation. The spatial isolation reinforces the sense of military exercises as staged performances reserving spectatorship primarily to selected military and political audiences and not general public. Nevertheless, some exercises are designed to occur in civilian spaces—such as NATO's urban warfare exercises, conduct of military logistics through public infrastructure, naval maneuvers to defend commercial harbors, and the safety of navigation, search and rescue operations as indirectly contributing to establishing control over commercial shipping lanes in a crisis. Such exercises project an actor's resilience and command of civilian infrastructures as dual use (cf. [Estonian Defense Forces 2024](#); [NATO JFCBS 2025](#)).

Military exercises become “socially” real for wider audiences through the mediated representation ([Mälksoo 2022](#), 65). These representations display fragmented narratives with a strong visual component: live fire drills involving land, sea, or air assets; choreographically assembled warship and aircraft formations; or camouflaged infantry and armored units enacting complex tactical scenarios, including the growing prominence of drone warfare. Considerations of secrecy and spatial isolation of exercising events lead to state-sponsored character of publicly available data. Thus, narratives are curated and incomplete, emphasizing certain locations, capabilities and maneuvers while withholding others from the public eye (cf. [Clem 2018](#), 132; [Vanderborgh 2024](#)).

In the case of authoritarian regimes, access to reliable and verifiable data on military exercises is even more constrained. It remains difficult to get a coherent quantitative overview of the Russian military exercises, with but a few studies providing datasets with a focus only on large-scale strategic maneuvers, and mostly discussing data from the period before 2022 (e.g., [Brzezinski and Varangis 2017](#); [Norberg 2018](#); [Ditrych and Ekman 2024](#)). Nevertheless, professional military observers treat this publicly available and curated data as valuable and, to a degree, credible source enabling informed speculation about actor's operational concepts, their threat perceptions and strategic intentions (cf. [Wintermans and Cox 2022](#)). Thus, awareness regarding curated representation and inevitable incompleteness of data disseminated by the state-sponsored sources is crucial for the scholarly treatment of military exercises.

This article draws on the reporting of the press-office of the Ministry of Defense and the state-sponsored media outlets disseminating the coverage of Russian Armed Forces military activities. For the study of ritualization processes, this data (albeit fragmented) enables the reconstruction of the narratives and correspondent visual representation. Treating the exercises as projected in public coverage, the analysis focuses on the ritualized modalities of Russia's strategic posture in the Baltic Sea. Accordingly, the findings should be read a reminder of the inevitable gap between the image of how activities are reported and factually occur. While the theoretical framework developed here emphasizes the intersubjective nature of strategic signaling, the empirical analysis necessarily remains limited to observable and reported posturing actions. The analysis accesses how exercises construct and project credible posture from the perspective of deterring actor. The engagement with the reception of such posturing actions by the audiences, intended and incidental, as well as drawing any conclusions about the actual

capabilities or combat readiness of the Russian military, remains beyond the scope of this article.

Ritualization and Strategic Posturing in the Russian Naval Drills in the Baltic Sea in 2022–2025

To ground this conceptual argument empirically, I examine some vignettes of Russian naval exercises from 2022 to 2025 in the Baltic Sea. The Baltic Sea constitutes one of the most proximate contact zones between NATO and Russia. In a conflict, achieving control over the Baltic Sea becomes the center of gravity for both actors. The Danish Straits serve as a critical chokepoint for access to and from the North Sea and Atlantic Ocean to the Baltic Sea. The defensive posture of NATO actors gravitates toward securing this maritime corridor to reinforce the Baltic states' defense in case of war. For Russia, it implies the focus on anti-access/area denial (A2/AD) capabilities, anchored in Kaliningrad, aiming to hinder NATO navigation in the surrounding waters. Respectively, sea denial successfully achieved in this area reinforces one's defensive posture by the ability to send support and supply to one's own troops and conversely deprives the adversary of this opportunity (cf. [Wermeling 2018](#); [Veebel and Ploom 2019](#)). The increase in naval engagement over the last decade demonstrates that the value of credible strategic posturing at sea is well appreciated by both Russia and NATO states ([Banka and Bussmann 2023](#); [Clem 2018](#)).⁸

The sea presents a particular site for deterrence. Unlike terrestrial environments that offer relatively stable reference points of landscapes, as well as natural boundaries like mountains or rivers, the maritime domain resists fixed representation and emerges as fundamentally undifferentiated space defined by fluidity and constant motion.⁹ Any engagement with the sea follows a structured processual logic: actors depart seawards, traverse the high seas, and ultimately return landward (cf. [Mälksoo 2022](#)). This points at the liminal quality inherent to the sea as a transient, threshold space ([Van Gennepe 1960](#); [Turner \[1969\] 2017](#); quoted in: [Mälksoo 2012](#); cf. [Turner 1979](#)).

Liminality suspends the boundaries of routine political interaction, enabling a heightened register of symbolic meaning which in turn reinforces the sea's distinction as a realm apart from the order of the land, along with the authority and structures bound to it. Indeed, the sea grants the actors greater freedom of political action than land.¹⁰ State borders at sea and the adjacent airspace in their literal meaning exist only on maps. Thus, the control of territorial waters and/or airspace heavily depends on a state's enforcement capability. For the permissive legal and customary frameworks governing naval operations in international waters, high seas are the ideal domain for unrestricted demonstration and employ-

⁸Despite heavy losses among Russian land forces in Ukraine, Russia's Baltic Fleet has been largely absent from Black Sea operations—apart from three Ropucha-class amphibious ships that transited the Turkish Straits just before the invasion and several Raptor-class patrol boats delivered overland ([Krutov 2022](#); [LaGrone 2022](#); [Wills 2023](#)). Despite the diminished amphibious assault capability, the fleet's overall force posture remains operational. Moreover, the recent operations of the Baltic Fleet's corvettes at Ladoga Lake, as well as their transit maneuvers from the Baltic Sea to the White Sea through the White Sea–Baltic Canal signifies evolving operational posture ([Adrians 2025](#)).

⁹In policy terms, the detachment with which maritime matters are perceived by both the public and expert audiences is encapsulated in the notion of “sea blindness” (cf. [Bueger and Edmunds 2017](#); [Larsson 2024](#)).

¹⁰Underwater nuclear tests conducted during the Cold War are an extreme historical example of this freedom. More recently, discussions within the Russian security expert community have entertained the notion of a “demonstrative nuclear explosion” at sea to deter NATO members from supporting Ukrainian defense effort ([Meduza 2024](#)).

ment of a wide array of platforms and capabilities, including live-firing exercises (Dombrowski and Reich 2024, 3). At the same time, for the sea is a naturally liminal realm, a naval maneuver does not merely signify an actor's presence: a warship is a symbolic embodiment of the state itself. Naval display thus becomes a form of interstate communication in its own right (Cohen 1981, 89).¹¹

Further, I frame the empirical analysis by identifying and discussing the ritual modalities of Russian naval exercises in the Baltic Sea between 2022–2025. In the next step, I probe how these ritualization modalities construct, project and sustain the image of Russian strategic posturing as credible in the Baltic Sea region.

Regularity, visibility and spatial configuration of naval activity

Russia's naval exercises occur regularly in the line with naval forces' training cycle schedule. A year commences with the tactical-level training which is followed by live firing maneuvers in spring. By June, the weather conditions get optimal, and the Baltic Sea gets "crowded" with concurrent military activity of Russia and the NATO states. Subsequently, the Baltic Fleet engages in shadowing maneuvers of NATO's BALTOPS, as well as of the exercises of Baltic coastal states. The cycle culminates in the annual strategic multi-fleet exercises which commence in the Baltic Sea after the Navy Day is celebrated on the last Sunday of July. Table 1 overviews the regular training cycle of the Russian naval forces and its spatial scope in the Baltic Sea.

Most of training activity recurs in designated areas along the Russian littoral zone. Naval maneuvers largely gravitate towards coastal defense in the Kaliningrad and Leningrad Oblasts. Due to the confined waters and elongated shape of the Baltic Sea, the Russian warships routinely seal off exercise zones within neighboring states' EEZs and may operate in very close proximity to their territorial waters. Moreover, the exercises typically include elements of navigation through key chokepoints of Danish Straits and the narrows of the Gulf of Finland. Amphibious assault on the unimproved coast and coastal defense maneuvers are usually conducted at the Khmelevka training grounds near Kaliningrad, and occasionally on the Russian islands in the Gulf of Finland (Bolshoi Tyuters, Gogland, and Moshchny) (cf. Minoborony Rossii 2019). Since 2017 expansion of training facilities of the Russian Navy took place, there have been documented events of corvettes' transition maneuvers from the Baltic Sea to Ladoga Lake and further to the north (Adrians 2025).

The regularity of naval presence across known locations ensures that any deviation—such as sudden snap exercises—will sharply stand out, amplifying the visibility of the readiness posture, and credibility effect of such maneuvers. A recent instance in this regard was the strategic multi-fleet "Ocean 2024" exercise, held in September 2024 and conducted off-schedule, just three weeks after the annual multi-fleet exercises (Zvezda 2024a; TASS 2024a). It was reportedly the largest exercise of its kind in 30 years (Vedomosti 2024). While the primary emphasis was put on blue water operations, a fleet formation of 30 vessels was deployed in the Baltic Sea to projecting credible image of the Russian Navy as capable to sustain large-scale naval operations over extended period of time (cf. Bott 2024).

¹¹For instance, U.S. President Donald Trump's statement about deploying two U.S. nuclear submarines "to the appropriate regions" in response to Russian ex-president Dmitry Medvedev's threats exemplifies how naval posturing enables deterrent signaling (Cancian and Park 2025).

The patterned execution of naval activity

Russian naval exercises comprise maneuvers executed in a recognizable and structured manner to develop requisite combat skills and operational readiness. To ensure predictability for command-and-control structures and reduce friction if entering an armed conflict, these maneuvers unfold in sequences of tactical elements, resembling a repertoire. These standardized elements are performed either as distinct actions in tactical-level training, or form integrated patterns within more complex scenarios. Together, they constitute the actor's concept of operations, guided by current military doctrine (Wintermans and Cox 2022).

Emplaced in conspicuous geography and performed with regularity and visibility, these patterned maneuvers acquire strategic meaning as coherent performances of a deterrent threat. Returning to Smith's concept of ritual, spatial emplacement and patterned action function as mutually reinforcing modalities in the process of ritualization of an actor's strategic posture (cf. Smith [1987] 1992, 103–109). These ritualized modalities *direct attention* of the audiences towards the geostrategic sensitivities of an actors, while patterns of manoeuvres performed actualize principles of military art as an interpretative convention against which the credibility of an actor's posture can be assessed by informed audiences, such as intelligence authority of adversaries (cf. Norberg 2023).

Localities in the Baltic Sea repeatedly used for demonstrative military activity acquire heightened "referent" value over time as allegorical terrains. The topographic features of these sites, such as sandy coast of Kaliningrad, or the island chain in the Gulf of Finland, and the proximity to NATO territory allow them to explicitly articulate the image of an anticipated conflict scenarios between Russia and NATO as plausible and immediate. The navigation of vessels through Lake Ladoga projects the potential scope of operations extending to the High North. The entire Baltic Sea, in this sense, becomes a posturing stage: regular overt naval maneuvers are increasingly complemented by continuous military activity across the Baltic Sea before, during, and after major exercises.¹⁴

Table 2 draws on reporting from the Baltic Fleet's press office, and media outlets, such as TASS, Zvezda and Srazh Baltiki (e.g., Gielewska et al. 2024; Komsomolskaya Pravda Kaliningrad 2025; Minoborony Rossii 2025; Strazh Baltiki 2024; TASS 2023a;b;b;c; Zvezda 2024b) and summarizes the approximate repertoire of the tactical elements demonstrated which are recurrent patters in the Russian naval exercises in the Baltic Sea between 2022 and 2025. Each element is categorized by its objective, its pattern reflecting the military logic underpinning the action, and the associated posturing function which corresponds to the conventional interpretation of the intent conveyed through such military activities.

While senior officials and intelligence agencies across the region share the assessment of Russian military power as significantly weakened by their resource-demanding operations in Ukraine, they also caution that Russian threat cannot be

¹⁴Similarly, the series of damage to critical undersea infrastructure in the Baltic Sea in years of 2022–2024, which are under investigation as deliberate sabotage in several coastal states, suggest that some grey-zone activities serve to complement strategic posturing. Interestingly, Russian strategic writing frames these activities as escalatory: "severing submarine cables in the Baltic Sea, then the Atlantic," preceded by a demonstrative show of capability (Trenin, Karaganov, and Avakyants 2024). These patterns exemplify how grey-zone tactics amplify the credibility of overt posturing by constructing a seamless continuum between overt and covert deterrent posturing action. This overt-to-covert activity patterns have long been argued to be a hallmark of Russian strategic deterrence concept (cf. Ven Bruusgard 2016; Adamsky 2024).

Table 1. The Russian Navy operations training cycle in the Baltic Sea.

Season	Type of Exercise	Spatial Scope
Summer (Jun–Jul)	Operational maneuvers of Baltic Fleet, shadowing NATO's BALTOPS	North-East and West of the Baltic Sea, NATO coastal states exercise areas
Summer (Jul–Aug)	Strategic-scale, multi-fleet exercises ("Ocean Shield" 2018–2023, "Ocean 2024," and "July Storm 2025") ¹²	Entire Baltic Sea basin, Danish straits and Gulf of Finland choke-points, Ladoga Lake and Baltic-White Sea
Autumn (Sep)	Strategic combined-arms exercises (Zapad series naval component, every 4 years, usually jointly with Belarus)	Russian coastal and near-shore waters
Year-round	Continuous tactical maneuvers of small formations (live-fire drills, combined arms)	Coastal and near-shore waters
Ad hoc	Snap exercises (short-notice readiness checks and drills), safety of navigation drills ¹³	Entire Baltic Sea basin, Danish straits, Gulf of Finland choke-points

¹²With the absence of maneuvers in the years 2021 and 2022, and under no specific label in 2024. ¹³Tactical-level engagements occur nearly on a weekly basis, as reported by "Strazh Baltiki," the official newspaper of the Baltic Fleet (Strazh Baltiki 2024). The safety of navigation exercise presents a novel tactical scenario, executed primarily in the West of Baltic Sea in April 2025, arguably as a response to the intensifying pressure on the Russian shadow fleet operations (TASS 2025a).

dismissed as hypothetical. Russian leadership believes that NATO challenges its scope for action in the Baltic Sea and thus turns more of its attention, both politically and militarily, to the Baltic Sea and the Nordics (e.g., LRT 2024; Piotrowski 2025; LRT 2025; DDIS 2025; Finnish Defense Forces 2025; Estonian Foreign Intelligence Service 2025; Norwegian Intelligence Service 2025; Defense Intelligence and Security Service Lithuania 2025). The findings presented in table 2 support this view: the repertoire of demonstrated tactical elements tends to offensive readiness posture. Some tactics exemplify the integration of recent combat experiences in Ukraine, whereas other demonstrate the command of the civilian maritime infrastructure as dual-use, and introduce elements which can be associated with hybrid warfare scenarios.

Symbolic attributes

In the process of ritualization, certain symbolic attributes enhance the affective resonance of the performance. Symbols imbue military action with references that extend beyond the immediate security concerns, tapping into the historical memory and identity narratives of participating and observing actors. Through these symbolic attributes, ritual-like action attempts to demonstrate that the values and forms of social organization to which the ritual testifies are neither arbitrary nor temporary, but follow naturally from the way the world is organized (Bell [1997] 2009, 135; cf. Mälksoo 2024). For the Russian naval exercises in the Baltic Sea, the following two symbolic references can be read as central in the ritualized enactments of strategic posture: 1. Russia in the Baltic region manifests itself as a leading naval power; 2. the Baltic region is a historical theater of Russia's confrontation with "the West."

The historical myth instrumentalized for this purpose can be traced back all the way to Peter I, who founded St. Petersburg following a resounding victory over the Swedish forces in the Great Northern War, and established the first Russian naval stronghold on the Baltic shores (cf. Hackmann 2022). Thus, the historical image of Russian military prowess became entwined with a claim to the Baltic region, and the transformation of Muscovy into a European empire with the establishment of a modern navy (cf. Herd 2022, 25–80). Russian President Vladimir Putin has remarked that he shares Emperor Alexander III's view that the nation's only true allies are its army and navy (TASS 2015). A recent statement

by Nikolai Patrushev, the head of the Maritime Collegium, draws on a similar association:

The Americans and their European allies have set a course toward the militarization of the Baltic Sea. Incidentally, this is a *traditional* strategy for the West. During the Crimean War, the British and French sought to seize Kronstadt, and in both World Wars, the Germans attempted to secure a foothold on the Russian shores of the Baltic. Our Baltic sailors have *always* crushed the aggressors' plans (Kommersant 2024).¹⁵

The annual strategic-level exercise of the Russian Navy is conducted directly following the Main Naval Parade in St. Petersburg and Kronstadt, held on the last Sunday of July.¹⁶ This makes sense from a logistical point of few, as many vessels will have already participated in the festivities. However, the transition from a ceremonial spectacle to naval maneuvers simultaneously articulates historic symbolism.

In July 1714, to celebrate the first victory in its modern naval history over Swedish forces at Gangut, Peter I, ordered a grand naval parade, leading the captured Swedish vessels from the Baltic Sea up the Neva River to his recently founded capital city of St. Petersburg (Widder 1987). Today, the president visits the old imperial capital to inspect *la fine fleur* of the Russian Navy during the parade. The festivities also involve a tour of such historical sites as the Peter-Paul Fortress, the Admiralty at Neva river, and Kronstadt sites, tracing locations along the same historic route. During the ceremony, an operational historical replica of Peter I's ship-of-the-line *Poltava* sails alongside modern Russian corvettes, frigates, and submarines (Kremlin 2022).

Russia's heyday of empire is not the only narrative tapped into. Moscow likewise draws on the more recent Soviet past. In 2024, the annual exercise following the parade was in turn followed by an additional exercise involving all fleets of the Russian Navy. This event, of a scale unprecedented in recent Russian history, was dubbed "Ocean-2024"—an explicit reference to the largest Soviet naval maneuvers in the period after WWII (Bott 2024). In this way, the Russian Navy engaged three centuries of naval history within a few weeks between July and September.

The sequence of these events—the heightened symbolism of the Naval Parade ceremony continued by show of force—consolidates the narrative framing of the Baltic Sea

¹⁵Emphasis mine.

¹⁶The main Naval Parade for Navy Day was canceled in July, 2025 due to security concerns. However, the strategic multi-fleet exercises took place in July-August 2025, this time under a new name "July Storm" (TASS 2025b,c).

Table 2. The approximate repertoire of the tactical elements establishing posturing patterns in Russian naval exercises in the Baltic Sea.

<i>Tactical Element</i>	<i>Objective</i>	<i>Pattern</i>	<i>Posturing</i>
1 Simulated missile launches by Bal and Bastion coastal defense missile systems targeting a mock enemy fleet	Coastal defense	Sustaining the coastal defensive perimeter integrity; sea control	A2/AD reach demonstration; ability to deny or disrupt adversary naval operations; precision strike readiness
2 Naval mine warfare maneuvering		Sea denial; ship survivability maneuvers; underwater warfare	
3 Repelling amphibious landing (Gulf of Finland, Khmelevka)		The amphibious force's integrated capability to deny enemy beach landings	Defensive readiness and capacity to hold the complex terrain (island, sandy shoreline) of strategically sensitive areas
4 Artillery and machine gun live-fire engagements against multiple target types, including simulated enemy warships, destruction of drone boats with shipboard artillery and heavy machine guns, and targeting aerial decoys	Defensive with offensive readiness posture	Sustaining operations against multiple threat vectors; layered defense capability; anti-drone warfare	Operational preparedness and readiness to engage at close range with diverse targets, including enemy ships, and various unmanned aerial and naval systems
5 Electromagnetic warfare		Integrated use of electromagnetic warfare capabilities, including jamming and counter-drone operations, reflecting adaptation to multi-domain threat environments and lessons from contemporary conflicts (e.g., Ukraine)	A2/AD reach demonstration in the non-kinetic spectrum; grey zone escalatory threat potential as the GPS signals disruption can affect both civilian and military aerial operations
6 Su-27 intercepts a mock enemy aircraft		Routine air defense and quick-reaction alert drills demonstrating readiness for aerial conflict in contested airspace; integration of advanced ballistic missile defense in layered defense posture	A2/AD reach demonstration; readiness to assert control over airspace and deny the air superiority for adversary
7 S-400 simulated missile interception		Anti-surface warfare and sea denial capability; integration of air power in joint naval and coastal defense operations	
8 Su-24/Su-30/Su-30SM2 simulated precision strike against various sea-, air- and land-based targets	Offensive		Operational preparedness and readiness for offensive engagement at various range and levels of escalation via nuclear-capable platforms and conventional long-range precision strike readiness demonstration

Table 2. Continued

	Tactical Element	Objective	Pattern	Posturing
9	Naval strike group (warships of the Baltic and Northern fleet) simulated launches of Zirkon, Kalibr and Moskit cruise missiles at sea-based and coast-based targets		Integrated strike readiness across fleets using advanced missile systems; emphasis on anti-surface warfare, sea control and strategic reach of advanced naval-based cruise missile, including hypersonic and nuclear capability	
10	Transition maneuvers from the Baltic to White Sea, and through the Danish Straits		Sea lines of communication control and denial; interoperability with the Northern Fleet	Readiness to reinforce and integrate with the Northern Fleet, ensuring control/denial of sea lines of communication and projecting force beyond the Baltic
11	Anti-submarine operations (small anti-submarine ships + Ka-27 helicopters, II Kilo-class submarines acting as a simulated target)	Defensive with offensive readiness posture	Anti-submarine warfare	Underscore domain awareness; regional ASW dominance; showcasing submarine warfare capability
12	Safety of navigation maneuvers		Sea lines of communication control and denial; hybrid threat scenarios; civilian vessels escort; anti-drone warfare	Readiness to intervene with force to protect operations of civilian fleet and counter a range of threats, including various drones
13	Counter-diversionary operation repelling a helicopter boarding and speed boats		Port security; hybrid threat scenarios	Readiness to provide naval support and intervene with force in protection of shadow fleet operations
14	Underwater sabotage defense (diver units)		Underwater warfare, hybrid threat scenarios	Readiness to operations on critical underwater and offshore infrastructure; underwater domain awareness

as a theater of Russian historical dominance.¹⁷ These performances tap into the sea's liminal quality, where the navigation of the Russian Navy's not only asserts the image of operational readiness and resolve, but relates contemporary operations to the claimed historical continuity of Russian naval dominance in the Baltic Sea. In this dramaturgy, the Baltic is more than a sea; it is a liminal ritual space where the Russian state emerges as a great-power out of contestation against the Western states, and continuously re-enacts past struggles to legitimize its assertive posturing in the present. This symbolic layer of meaning purports to magnify the image of Russian resilience amid the challenges of the present-day, and Moscow's resolve to confront "the collective West" in the Baltic, lending this claim a long-durée dimension.

Conclusion

This article presents a study of how the ritualization of coercive signaling action enables actors to frame and to project credibility of their military activity so that audiences—state actors, the media and the public—"see" deterrence as an embodied and spatialized phenomenon. The projections of deterrent credibility rely not solely on the demonstration of military capability. Instead, three modalities of posturing as ritualized action are central to construct and project credibility: spatially configured and visually defined, regular presence and patterned action drawing on symbolic attributes.

I probe the ritual logics and spatial grammar underlying Russian naval exercises in the Baltic Sea, as observed between 2022 and 2025. Spatial configuration and patterned actions are mutually reinforcing modalities in ritualization of strategic posturing; Russian maneuvers regularly occur in localities that resemble NATO's coastal geographies and/or are situated in direct proximity to NATO's territorial waters, simulating naval combat and using the terrain's resemblance to create a geographic allegory that projects realistic scenarios of amphibious landings on adversaries' shores. Table 2 identifies 14 tactical elements which project offensive readiness posture for naval combat and demonstrate dual-use capabilities relevant for hybrid scenarios. By linking these elements, Russian strategic posturing engage with the ongoing allegations of Moscow's grey-zone operations in the Baltic Sea, and consolidate credibility projection as continuous from wartime to peacetime. Finally, the Russian Navy materializes the symbolic geography of the "Russian" Baltic: the spectacular Main Naval Parade continues to the annual naval exercises, and thus symbolically draws the historical lineage of the Russian imperial and Soviet naval power. The assertive Russian posture is thus presented as a rightful claim for the dominance in the Baltic region.

Ultimately, the findings presented here support the proposition that deterrence credibility emerges as an intersubjectively constituted social fact (cf. Vuori 2016; Lupovici, 2016; Mälksoo 2021). Through the ritualized modalities of its enactment, military activity is rendered into a politically salient strategic posture which frames, projects and sustains the image of deterrent credibility. This framework lays foundation for a better understanding how actors seek deterrent credibility in empirically elusive and routinized contexts of general deterrence. This article suggests a transferable analytical lens for examining how military activities contribute to the

framing, projection, and perception of strategic posturing in other geopolitical contexts, for instance in the Middle East and the Indo-Pacific. Future research could study how spatiality matters for signaling effectiveness and facilitates interactional dynamics of credibility perception and deterrence success of failure.

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¹⁷In February 2024, Russian President Vladimir Putin reintroduced the Leningrad Military District in reaction to Finland's accession to NATO. While this move undoubtedly stands for signals a more concentrated orientation to continue military build-up on Russia's northwestern flank, it also holds certain symbolic legacy of confrontation as the district commanded Soviet aggression against Finland and Baltic republics in 1940s (Rossiiskaya Gazeta 2024; Kukkola 2024).

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